

Amplifying Children's Voices

Principles, Challenges, and Pathways for
Effective Complaints Processes in Care
– Phase One Evidence and Insights

November 2020

Amplifying Children’s Voices Principles, Challenges, and Pathways for Effective Complaints Processes in Care – Phase One Evidence and Insights

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Contents

Introduction	3
Key Principles	4
Methods.....	5
Involving children in research and design.....	5
Whaipanga: Beneficence	7
Kaitiakitanga: Guardianship and Protection	12
The Complaints Journey.....	14
The Help-seeking Process	14
The Complaints Process	29
Principles of effective complaints systems	29
Tools used to receive complaints.....	31
Making a complaint.....	33
Enablers for complaining	35
Traversing the process	37
General principles	46
Principles of communicating with children and young people.....	46
Technology.....	49
Appendices.....	54
Appendix One: UN Declarations	54
The International Human Rights Framework for Indigenous Children and Youth	54
Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)	54
References	55

Introduction

This report covers Phase One of the Children’s Voices research project which will support the Ombudsman to design new communications channels and content that will support and facilitate the Children in Care Complaints process.

This report consists of the findings of an evidence scan and more than 20 qualitative interviews conducted in September and October 2020. It is intended to provide a knowledge base that will support Phase Two of this project, which is the gathering of the voices of children and young people in care (and their whānau and families), as well as the views of adult helpers.

We have chosen to present the two data sources (literature and interviews) alongside each other throughout the document, as we believe both sources have equal value and make more sense when they are read together. Also, in another departure from standard practice, we have chosen to run the executive summary down the side of the findings, enabling readers who want to skim through to quickly find and ‘dip’ into parts where they may wish to learn more.

Method

Interviews

We interviewed 24 professionals from 20 organisations that work, or have worked in some way, with children and young people in care.

Interviews were conducted in person, via Zoom or by phone. Each interview was transcribed, and key points were unpacked and written on to post-it notes. The research team then themed and headlined the data using a constant comparative process (right).

Key Principles

Several key principles emerged from our interviews and evidence scan. We believe these principles have value in terms of guiding the approach of the research and framing any solutions that arise from this process.

In short, the principles are:

1. **Whaipāinga (beneficence).** Both the research and solution should be of primary benefit to children and young people. Their use should result in positive change.
2. **Kaitiakitanga (guardianship and protection).** Harm to children and young people must not occur either through the research or use of the tools.
3. **Aro ā-tamariki (child-centred).** Development of the solution must involve children and young people and must be easy and safe for children and young people to use.
4. **Whakaoranga (restorative).** The research and the solution should recognise children and young people's experience of trauma. The solution should be focussed on restoration and healing.
5. **Tūāpāpā ā-tikanga (rights-based).** The research and the solution should recognise and promote the rights of children and young people protected in conventions such as The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCROC), Article 7 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and Articles 21 and 22 of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP)¹.
6. **Mana taurite (equity).** All children and young people should have equal access to the processes regardless of their abilities and/or means. Equity is about equity of outcome as much as access to a process and requires being free of conscious and unconscious bias.

These principles form the foundation of our approach to this research project.

¹ These articles are appended.

Methods

The aims and scope of this research, and any proposed solutions, pose five main challenges that need to be addressed ethically and methodologically. Many of the child and youth participants in this project will be:

- Removed from their families and whānau to be taken into state care
- Between 8 and 17, including pregnant mums who are expecting that their child/ren will be removed at birth
- Likely to have experienced significant physical and/or emotional harm
- Have a compromised ability to cope with (perceived) threats to their safety or wellbeing
- Be mistrustful of adults.

There may well be other challenges that emerge as we begin speaking with the children and young people during the project. We will operate on the basis of mitigating risk through the research design and using the principle of 'reflect and adapt' to adjust and improve our approach as we learn.

While we recognise that vulnerable children need care and protection, we also recognise that they have agency and experience, skills and knowledge to contribute. Furthermore, they don't need to be 'given' a voice, they already have one, but the problem is they sometimes choose to not speak up because it's too risky or, in their view, not worth it².

This research presents some methodological challenges, primarily due to the vulnerability of research participants.

Involving children in research and design

Since the beginning of the century, there has been increased interest in the participation of children and young people in research that affects them. There are, however, inherent power relations at work when researchers report views about children and young people without asking them for their own views and

Views about the needs of children and young people should not be reported without their input.

² Metzger, N., Savaii, K., McKee, A. & Kedge, S., (2018). *Listening to young peoples' experiences of communication within the youth justice sector in New Zealand*. Point Research and Talking Trouble.

experiences.

The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child³ is regarded widely as the foundation for children's relationships with the adult, institutional and governmental contexts in which they live. This includes their right to an adequate standard of living and to be protected from all forms of abuse, neglect and violence. The direct participation of children and young people in research has been strengthened by Article 12 of the UNCROC, which requires that children be given meaningful opportunities to express their views and be heard on matters that affect them. Excluding 'vulnerable' groups of children (such as children who have experienced harm or are at increased risk of harm) denies them the right to participation afforded to other children. Children⁴ are not 'little adults'; they have unique lives, views, needs and preferences.

Researchers and designers are increasingly involving children in research and design processes to increase the usability and accuracy, to address power and control, and to strengthen the link between children, policy and practices⁵.

From a practical standpoint, the construction of a safe, inclusive and productive research and design process is challenging when dealing with vulnerable groups of children. To address this challenge, we have reviewed the literature about research and design with vulnerable children to build on our experience of working in this space. Two of our foundational principles, beneficence and protection, are intended to protect against the above-mentioned challenges. Beneficence and protection have guided the development of our approach and the selection of methods for involving children and young people in this project.

Article 12 of UNCROC strengthens the direct participation of children and young people in research.

Excluding children and young people based on their vulnerability denies them the right to participation.

The approach of this research has been guided primarily by the principles of *whaipainga* (beneficence) and *kaitiakitanga* (guardianship and protection).

³ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/crc.aspx>

⁴ Consistent with the literature, we define children as people under 18 years of age.

⁵ For example, Bradbury-Jones, C. et al, 2018. *The complexities and contradictions in participatory research with vulnerable children and young people: A qualitative systematic review. Social Science and Medicine*. Mulvale, A. et al, 2016. *Applying experience-based co-design with vulnerable populations: lessons from a systematic review of methods to involve patients, families and service providers in child and youth mental health service improvement. Patient Experience Journal*.

Whaipaianga: Beneficence

Our interviewees would like to see a research and design process that delivers clear benefits to children and young people who participate. They were very clear that for children and young people to benefit from the research and design process, it needs to respond to their communication needs and preferences, utilise existing relationships with trusted people and use multiple methods of engagement.

There was also general agreement that whilst consulting a reasonable number of children and young people would be of some benefit, having a smaller number of interested participants take part in more meaningful ways would be of greater benefit to both them and the research process.

There is extensive literature about ethical and methodological issues and approaches in research and design involving children⁶.

The research process should deliver clear benefits to the children and young people who participate.

Communication needs

Researchers across the globe are just beginning to understand the relationship between childhood trauma and the types of communication and behavioural issues commonly seen in care-experienced children⁷. Recent neuroscience developments demonstrate that ongoing ruptures in early interpersonal relationships and the effects of cumulative and prolonged levels of stress are likely to affect the underlying structure and function of the developing brain, particularly the executive functions that are critical to communication and behaviour such as self-regulation, working memory and cognitive flexibility⁸. Complex trauma is therefore linked to externalizing behaviours such as difficulty concentrating,

The method should allow participation from children using a range of communication needs and preferences.

⁶ Thabrew, H., Fleming T., Hetrick S., and Merry S, (2018). *Co-design of eHealth interventions with children and young people*. *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 9:481

⁷ Wolpaw, R., Johnson, M. M., Hertel, R., & Kincaid, S. O. (2009). *The heart of learning and teaching: Compassion, resiliency, and academic success*. Olympia: Washington State Office of Superintendent of Public Instruction (OSPI) Compassionate Schools.

⁸ Center on the Developing Child (2007). *The Impact of Early Adversity on Child Development (InBrief)*. Retrieved from www.developingchild.harvard.edu.

distractibility, and the inability to remain seated⁹.

Although it may be tempting to exclude 'difficult' or 'challenging' young people from research processes, it is also important to address their needs if an intervention is likely to be useful to its intended audience and serve its legislated purpose. Importantly, diverse users may have different needs and preferences. For example, young people who are not distressed are likely to find help-seeking easier than those with depression¹⁰. Furthermore, even within seemingly similar groups, preferences can be diverse and conflicting. Where multiple types of users are engaged, care needs to be taken to balance their needs or to meet the needs of some users well. Trying to please everyone with one design can lead to the creation of a universally unsatisfactory tool. In such situations, it may be more useful to segment an audience and interventions¹¹.

Researchers and designers have found that hearing from children was easiest when children were allowed some meaningful activity (e.g. drawing, playing) during the interview¹². Furthermore, the engagement of young people can be improved with the use of culturally relevant (including youth-, pop- and ethnic-culture) concepts and motifs, settings and props¹³. Thabrew et al reported that some young people considered that a gamified, playful interface was important for engagement and that early intervention approaches would be the most desirable and powerful; however, others considered that a serious, to-the-point, simple interface was essential and that games would be trivialising¹⁴.

Children in a study about online strategies were found to be more talkative when they could show things on a computer. They were more spontaneous when they could sit with the researcher at the computer after which the researcher could more easily talk with them¹⁵.

Hearing from children is easiest when they can participate in an activity.

Concepts and settings should be culturally relevant.

Gamified interfaces can be powerful; however, they should not trivialise the subject matter.

Children may be more talkative when they can show things on a computer.

⁹ Wolpow et al. 2009

¹⁰ Mulvale, A. et al, 2016.

¹¹ Ibid

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Thabrew, H et al., 2018

¹⁵ Barbovschi, M. et al, 2013. *Innovative approaches for investigating how children understand risk in new media: dealing with methodological and ethical challenges*. EU Kids Online.

Interviews and focus groups offer a safe space for youth to share experiences, which was especially important when participants were critical of service providers. Focus groups enabled them to gain additional insight compared to individual interviews¹⁶.

Overall, researchers consider that using multiple methods of engagement for children and young people, particularly those tailored to their communication needs and preferences, is a valuable approach that offers insights that may be difficult to access through a single method of data collection¹⁷.

Multiple methods of engagement are preferable.

Utilising existing relationships

Research into social work practice suggests that deep or valuable communication with care-experienced children is near impossible without a relationship. For social workers, this means taking time to build a relationship over several interactions¹⁸. This, however, is problematic for researchers who may be time- or budget-bound to only have one interaction with a child or young person. In this instance, it is suggested that communication with care-experienced children is mediated and supported by an adult that the child or young person trusts¹⁹.

Deep communication with care-experienced children is almost impossible without a relationship.

Peer research, in which children and young people are active and equal agents in the production of knowledge and services has been utilised successfully in research around the experiences of children in care in Wales and England. It is also noted that overseas researchers who looked at children's use of technology successfully used older children (14–15-year olds) to speak with slightly younger children (8–12-year-olds)²⁰. Younger children were excited about being able to engage with the older children, which meant they may have spoken more freely than they might have done with adults.

Peer research with children in care has been successfully undertaken in Wales and England.

¹⁶ Mulvale, A. et al, 2016.

¹⁷ Darbyshire, P; MacDougall, C and Schiller, W., (2005) Multiple methods in qualitative research with children: more insight or just more? *Qualitative Research* 5(4) 417-436

¹⁸ Broadhurst K and Mason C (2014) Social work beyond the VDU: Foregrounding co-presence in situated practice— why face-to-face practice matters, *British Journal of Social Work*, 44, 3, 578-95

¹⁹ Morrison, F. (2016) Social workers' communication with children and young people in practice. Insight 34, IRISS <https://www.iriss.org.uk/resources/insights/social-workers-communication-children-and-young-people-practice>

²⁰ Barbovschi, M. et al, 2013.

Adults were available in case of any problems and had to work hard at keeping the discussions focussed. This approach is useful in some settings, depending on the capabilities of other children and their willingness to participate on this basis.

Participatory approaches

'Participatory' approaches are becoming more common and nuanced to minimise – as far as practical – adults' control over knowledge production to further elucidate children's experiences, views and service needs and preferences. Participatory approaches facilitate the active involvement of participants in research, beyond providing data²¹. Instead of research *about* or *on* children, participatory research is conducted *with* or *by* children, which means children play a significant and equivalent role to adult researchers in some or all stages of the research process.

Participatory approaches can help vulnerable children challenge the status-quo and adult-dominated spaces, discourses and decisions that affect them. Empowering children who have been traumatised to be heard and involved in developing solutions can give them a sense of being valued, which is often something that has been missing in their lives²².

The concept of *Āta* can help shape and guide understandings of relationship and wellbeing in a participatory context and is a key element when considering designing participatory processes. *Āta* focusses on relationships, negotiating boundaries, and working to create and hold safe space. Importantly, it draws on holistic principles of Te Ao Māori such as *te whakatinana* (to enact), *te whakatauirā* (to model), *te mahitahi* (to function together) and *te whakawhitiwhiti whakaaro* (to exchange viewpoints openly acknowledging the integrity of the other)²³. Framing the participatory approach using these principles will ensure a respectful and responsive process, which is particularly important when working with vulnerable populations.

Participatory methods are those that are *with* or *by* children and young people, where they play a significant and equivalent role to adult researchers.

Participatory approaches can help vulnerable children challenge the adult-dominated status quo.

Āta is a kaupapa Māori concept which focusses on relationships, negotiating boundaries, and working to create and hold safe space

²¹ Bradbury-Jones, C. et al, 2018.

²² Ibid.

²³ Pohatu, T.W. (2004). *Āta*: growing respectful relationships. He Pukenga Korero, 8(1): 1-8.

There is an emerging field of participatory design called co-design, and experience-based co-design, which is a participatory approach to involving intended service- or product-users in the design process. Co-design involves learning from users and involving them in iterating and testing options and developing the final/preferred end-product across the entire design process. It is an active, collaborative process between researchers, designers, developers and users as 'experts. Participants not only *say* what they want from the intervention or service, they also actively *use* service prototypes and inform solutions. New Zealand researchers who designed eHealth interventions with young people warn that co-design must be a genuine process, not a renamed consultation process. They say:

The term 'co-design' is sometimes incorrectly applied to include processes, more correctly termed 'consultation' or 'engagement' during which users' views on a need, idea or product are sought in a limited manner. Co-design aims for better design based on a richer, deeper understanding of what users know, feel and even dream²⁴.

Key lessons from a review of experience-based co-design projects included the importance of organisation 'buy-in' from the start to both the process and implementation to avoid disappointment and wasting participants' (including children's) time²⁵. Core values of co-design are translating knowledge into action, involving end-users and self-determination to subvert traditional power relations between 'researcher' and 'researched'²⁶. Experience-based codesign recognises the importance of safety, functionality and usability²⁷. In their review of involving children in design processes, Mulvale²⁸ and Thabrew²⁹ found that power imbalances for vulnerable populations could be addressed by using storytelling and visual media, employing youth as research partners, establishing equal status among participants, offering counselling support, paying particular attention to confidentiality, scheduling

Co-design is a participatory approach that involves users in iterating and testing options; however, care should be taken to ensure the co-design process is not simply a re-named form of consultation.

Using storytelling, visual media, employing youth as research partners, establishing equal status among participants, and having skilled facilitators can help to mitigate power imbalances in a co-design process.

²⁴ Thabrew, H. et al, 2018

²⁵ Mulvale, A. et al, 2016.

²⁶ *ibid.*

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ *ibid.*

²⁹ Thabrew, H. et al, 2018.

frequent breaks, and having skilled interviewers and facilitators.

Kaitiakitanga: Guardianship and Protection

Children in care are vulnerable. They have either been harmed and/or are at greater risk of harm compared to most children in the wider population. Given this, we have identified a number of challenges and solutions to keeping our project team members and the children we learn from safe.

1. Building trust.

Research involving vulnerable groups needs an extensive warm-up phase to allow participants to lose their fear of reporting³⁰. The presence of familiar adults helps children feel more comfortable. Involving young people as group discussion leaders also helps children feel comfortable sharing.

2. Harmful situations

Problematic or even harmful situations may also be revealed spontaneously during data collection sessions with children. Such situations demand both the researcher's sensitivity and ad hoc adaptability to novel/spontaneous challenges.

Liamputtong (2007) notes vulnerable groups who may lack the ability to withdraw from the research if they become uncomfortable or raise the issue if they experience harm. She stresses the need for researchers to recognise that continuing an interview with participants who might not feel they can withdraw causes harm.

3. Training project team staff

A "kit" will be prepared for the group discussion leaders, including a semi-structured interview guide and safety protocols, i.e. what to do if an interviewee says they

Challenges and solutions to keeping children, young people and the project team safe include building trust, dealing effectively with potentially harmful situations and good training for the project team.

³⁰ Barbovschi, M. et al, 2013.

need, or appears to need, emotional support³¹.

³¹ Hearn, J., Andersson, K. & Cowburn, M. (2007) Background Paper on Guidelines for Researchers on Doing Research with Perpetrators of Sexual Violence. Sexual Violence Research Initiative, Pretoria, South Africa

The Complaints Journey

The Help-seeking Process

What is 'help-seeking' and how does it apply to complaints?

There are few specific, agreed upon definitions of 'help-seeking behaviour' in the adolescent health and development literature. Typically, the help-seeking literature is focussed on services for mental health issues or for problem-related psychosocial needs such as homelessness, sexual and interpersonal violence, relationship stresses or acute financial needs. In 2007, however a report for the World Health Organization proposed to extend the definition to:

Any action or activity carried out by an adolescent who perceives herself/himself as needing personal, psychological, affective assistance or health or social services, with the purpose of meeting this need in a positive way³².

Whilst there are very few (if any) references in the literature to children and young people's help-seeking for complaints resolution³³, we believe a review of help-seeking is useful to understand the motivations, enablers and barriers around seeking help to resolve complaints, and well as to shed some light on what young people are looking for in terms of processes and methods when they interact with 'official' services.

Most literature is focussed on services for mental health or psychosocial needs; however, it is still useful for helping to understand motivations, barriers and enablers around seeking help to resolve complaints.

The help-seeking journey

The model presented in Figure 1 represents a theoretical model of help-seeking towards a complaint resolution. The help-seeking process includes several stages:

The help-seeking process towards complaints

³²Barker, G. (2007). *Adolescents, social support and help-seeking behaviour: an international literature review and programme consultation with recommendations for action*. World Health Organisation.

³³ Throughout this report, we refer to the 'child or young person' as the help seeker, however it is likely that the help seekers will be a child or young person *and* their helper/advocate.

1) An awareness that there is a situation or issue that doesn't 'feel right'

2) problem recognition

3) perceived need for help (realising that help is needed to solve the problem)

4) evaluating available help options (whether an appropriate source of help is available).

Following the help-seeking journey, there are two stages of resolution:

1) dealing with the problem, either through mediation, restoration or through initiating a formal complaints process and

2) traversing the process.

The resolution stages are covered in this report in the Complaints Journey on page 15.

Information and resources, and formal and informal helpers are key supports in the helping journey for young people. The information and resources available should be suitable for both the child or young person *and* their informal or formal helpers, as both parties will consult these at different parts of the process.

The research identifies several barriers and enablers to help-seeking. Similarly, whether the experience is positive or negative will also impact the child or young person's journey through the help-seeking process, with most stopping after a negative experience.

resolution consists of several stages:

1. Awareness
2. Problem recognition
3. Perceived need for help
4. Evaluating available and appropriate help options.

Information and helpers are key supports.

Most young people will stop if the process is too hard or their experience is negative.

Figure 1: Model of help-seeking towards a complaint resolution

Figure 1 is based on several theoretical models of help-seeking. One of the commonly referenced models in the literature, The Stage Model of Help Seeking, was devised by Kessler and colleagues in 1981³⁴. This model proposes three stages of help seeking:

- 1) problem recognition (i.e., recognising that something isn't OK)
- 2) perceived need for help (believing that help is needed to resolve the issue)
- 3) obtaining help, that is, formal help seeking.

In 2017, following research with Canadian teens in foster care, researchers Emily Johnson and Rosanne Menna identified an additional step: evaluating available sources of help to determine whether the source has been "in their shoes" or has a unique understanding of their situation³⁵.

Having access to information and resources, and formal and informal helpers is critical at all the stages of the help-seeking and complaints journey. Having these supports does not guarantee that a young person will progress through the different stages however, as poor information and poor helpers can be barriers in just the same way that good information and good help are enablers. Later in this section we will look at what comprises both good and poor information and help. For now, however, we look at each stage of the journey towards complaints resolution. Note that the principles at each stage of the journey below apply whether the help seeker is a child or young person, or a formal or informal helper.

Having access to information and resources, and formal and informal helpers is critical at all the stages of a young person's help-seeking and complaints journey.

Four stages of help seeking

1. Situation

Before seeking help, individuals must first identify a problem³⁶. A crucial factor in this is that a child or young person has

Children and young people who can understand and name their feelings and have

³⁴ Kessler, R. C., Brown, R. L., & Broman, C. L. (1981). Sex differences in psychiatric help-seeking: Evidence from four large-scale surveys. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 22, 49–64. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2136367>.

³⁵ Johnson, E., & Menna, R. (2017). Help seeking among adolescents in foster care: A qualitative study. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 76, 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.03.002>

³⁶ Kessler et al., 1981

knowledge or emotional awareness of their needs³⁷. Thus, while they may or may not be able to describe exactly what the breach of their rights or entitlement is at this point, they do know that something doesn't feel right.

Getting children and young people in care to understand and name their feelings is important to this process. Some interviewees felt that not every child and young person in care is in a space or place where discussions about how they are feeling and what is happening is 'normal'.

If [children and young] people are getting good emotional regulation support in exploring their feelings and exploring their interactions with other people, if they're getting a lot of that sort of stuff, then that is going to give them a better sense of what may or may not be a complaint. (Interviewee)

Low emotional awareness is likely to be a significant barrier to help seeking; research has found that 16–18-year-olds low in emotional awareness are the least likely to seek help from friends/family and most likely to refuse help from anyone³⁸.

access to trusted adults are more likely to seek help.

Children and young people who are not in emotionally or physically safe spaces are unlikely to seek help

2. Recognise problem

In 2012, the Office of the Children's Commissioner found that a number of reviews of complaints processes have identified a *lack of knowledge about their rights* as a primary barrier to entering a complaints process.

Those we interviewed also cited this as a barrier for children and young people entering a complaints process, particularly knowing what their rights are and identifying if these are not being met. We heard from several people that a 'rights focus' was a necessary precursor to a complaints process, particularly helping children and young people in care recognise the difference between grievances and situations that could result in a complaint, and how to proceed with both.

Children and young people must have access to information about their rights and entitlements to begin help-seeking towards a complaints process.

³⁷ Johnson, E. (2019). Help Seeking Behaviours of Adolescents in Foster Care: Multiple . <https://scholar.uwindsor.ca/etd/7811> : Electronic Theses and Dissertations. 7811.

³⁸ Rickwood, D., Deane, F. P., Wilson, C. J., & Ciarrochi, J. (2005). Young people's help-seeking for mental health problems. *Australian e-Journal for the Advancement of Mental Health*, 4, 1–34 [Link](#)

Interviewees also wanted some way to help young people distinguish between something that was worrying or bothering them, and something that could be the subject of a complaint. One felt that:

'Young people have a role to play being rights defenders for others. They could say 'Here's our complaints process and here's some advice young people had about stuff that might be worrying you'. That way if somebody stole your stuff, you don't need to complain to the Ombudsman, just tell the kid to leave your stuff alone.'

Children's Rights

In Aotearoa, there are a range of policies and strategies aimed at ensuring that children's rights are protected, including the Agenda for Children and the Youth Development Strategy Aotearoa. There are several international charters that are designed to protect the rights of children and young people. New Zealand is a signatory to the International Human Rights framework for Indigenous Children and Youth, Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCROC).

UNCROC sets out the rights of children, aged 0 to 18 years, and the responsibilities of governments to fulfil those rights. UNCROC requires governments to ensure that the best interests of the child come first where decisions, laws or services involve children and includes who is responsible to ensure the rights of children are met, in particular:

Article 3.1 - In all actions concerning children, whether undertaken by public or private social welfare institutions, courts of law, administrative authorities or legislative bodies, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration.

Article 12.1 - States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child.

Article 12.2 - For this purpose, the child shall in particular be

Users need information and advice from young people about the differences between what's a worry and what's a complaint

Aotearoa has a range of strategies and process aimed at protecting children's rights.

United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCROC) requires governments to ensure that the best interests of the child come first where decisions, laws or services involve children.

provided the opportunity to be heard in any judicial and administrative proceedings affecting the child, either directly, or through a representative or an appropriate body, in a manner consistent with the procedural rules of national law.

Given the over-representation of pēpi, tamariki and rangatahi Māori within the care and protection system, it is also appropriate to consider the role of Te Tiriti O Waitangi (the Treaty of Waitangi). The treaty upholds the rights of pēpi, tamariki and rangatahi Māori to have inequalities reduced and experience the same privileges as tauwiwi³⁹. A Waitangi Tribunal hearing into Oranga Tamariki has recently concluded, with closing statements to be made at the end of November 2020. Regardless of the findings, it is still valuable to consider Te Tiriti O Waitangi as a critical document in upholding the rights of pēpi, tamariki and rangatahi Māori, and their right to complain when these are breached.

In July 2019, Oranga Tamariki introduced National Care Standards, which include, among other things, a child-friendly statement of rights and My Rights My Voice cards⁴⁰ designed to help children and young people understand what they're entitled to under the Care Standards. It is unclear, however, what the uptake of these resources is, whether these are being presented to children and young people in care, and how well they understand the information. Phase Two of this project will include a question for children and young people in care around their knowledge of their rights (and rights information will be shared with them if they don't).

Te Tiriti O Waitangi upholds the rights of pēpi, tamariki and rangatahi Māori to have inequalities reduced and experience the same privileges as tauwiwi.

Oranga Tamariki recently introduced National Care Standards, which a child-friendly statement of rights and My Rights My Voice cards.

³⁹ Mackenzie, D. & Herbert, R (2017) Don't tell me your problems: The Family Court complaints and appeals landscape. The Backbone Collective

⁴⁰ <https://www.orangatamariki.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Children-in-our-care/Care-Standards/My-rights-my-voice-booklet.pdf>

Figure 2: Child Statement of Rights: Oranga Tamariki

3. Recognise need for help

Research with young people in care has found that there are varying levels of awareness that help is needed. Whilst some people can articulate a need for help, others don't see either that they need help, or that their issue is one for which help might be available⁴¹.

Several reviews of complaints processes have found that children and young people may be unlikely or unwilling to make a complaint because they lack knowledge about both their rights, and the complaints system itself⁴².

Several of our interviewees also felt that very few children and young people in care are aware that they can voice concerns over their care and treatment, let alone that there is a complaints process open to and available for children and young people in care.

I haven't heard of any young person in care utilising processes that are available to young people in care, to make a complaint, to raise questions or

Many young people don't recognise they need help, or that help is available.

Some young people don't believe they need or deserve help.

⁴¹ Johnson & Menna, 2017

⁴² Office of the Children's Commissioner. (2012). *A Review of the Child, Youth and Family Complaints Resolution Policy and Procedure: Recommendations on how Child, Youth and Family can take a Child-Centred Approach to Complaints Resolution*. Wellington, New Zealand: [Link](#)

*whatever about the experiences they're having.
(Interviewee)*

We heard from our interviewees that the situation was even more difficult for children and young people with communication issues and/or disabilities, and that any process would need to be accessible for a range of abilities and communication levels.

Other interviewees also suggested a campaign like the "It's OK" campaign which let children and young people in care know that "it's ok to tell someone" if they're not happy.

Information must be suitable for a range of communication abilities.

4. Evaluate available options

Crucial to the help-seeking process is an awareness of where to access help, as without knowing where to access support, help-seeking cannot be an option. The 2012 OCC review of the Child, Youth and Family (now Oranga Tamariki) complaints process found that most of the 20 participants did not know how to make a complaint if they were unhappy about something or had not been treated well.

Information about the complaints system should be easy to find. Research with young people in New Zealand suggests that young people only access support and services when they 'trip over' them⁴³. Ideally, the complaints system should be taken to the young person, rather than waiting for the child or young person to find the system⁴⁴. Working with places where children and young people already access help and information, such as school counsellors, child and youth support services such as Youthline, 0800 Whats Up or Kidsline may make it easier to take the complaints system to them.

Young people tend to only access support and services when they 'trip over' them.

Most of the 20 child and youth participants in the 2012 OCC review felt that rights and complaints information could be made available on a website. They also wanted to be given this information by their social workers. Some participants wanted a more proactive approach, whereby a support adult (not their

⁴³ Woodley, A., Davis, R., & Metzger, N. (2013). *Breaking the silence but keeping secrets: What young people want to address sexual violence*. Auckland: Tu Wahine Trust and HELP (Auckland Sexual Abuse HELP Foundation)

⁴⁴ Western Australia Commissioner for Children and Young People: Complaints Guidelines

social worker) would get in touch with them every three months to see how things were going, and others asked that someone could check in once a year to see if they had any complaints.

Unsurprisingly, research on care-experienced children and young people shows they have very little faith in complaints processes. This is because children may be fearful of negative repercussions or that they have attempted to complain but their voices were not heard⁴⁵. This view was supported by many of our interviewees, who believed it was likely that most children and young people in care have spoken up before, or tried to speak up, about things they are unhappy with to no avail⁴⁶. We also had anecdotal feedback that young people have made complaints to Oranga Tamariki, only for these to be 'shelved' until the young person reaches 18 and ages out of the system (and therefore the complaint no longer needs to be dealt with). For our interviewees, any complaints process will therefore be competing with the voice in the heads of children and young people in care that says, *"What's the use, no one's going to listen, nothing will happen, I'm powerless"⁴⁷*.

It is, therefore, no guarantee that children and young people will complain once they recognise that a complaint can be made. There is one crucial final step in the help-seeking journey towards complaints resolution, which is evaluation of whether *appropriate* sources of help are available⁴⁸.

Johnson and Menna⁴⁹ found that even after an appraisal for help, a major driver for young people in foster care towards engagement in a process was whether appropriate help was available, particularly from a source that appeared to be familiar with their situation and where they didn't feel they had to start "from the beginning".

Interviewees we spoke to in phase one felt that children and young people are unlikely to open up about what's going on until a trusted relationship is formed, which can take time. As

Children and young people are unlikely to engage in a complaints process if they have had a previous poor experience with speaking up.

Children and young people more likely to engage if the source of help appears familiar with situation of children and young people in care.

⁴⁵ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

⁴⁶ We heard several examples during our interviews where it was feasible that complaints could have been made but weren't.

⁴⁷ Interviewee statement

⁴⁸ Ibid

⁴⁹ Johnson & Menna, 2017

one interviewee said:

Children in care have lost their voice. Their voice is taken from them the day they are taken from their parents.

A lack of initial trust may be exacerbated for children and young people by a fear they will not be believed that there will be negative consequences for them or their whānau or those who are caring for them, or that their situation would require too much explanation. We also heard that young people often feel judged in their communications with adults, and do not want to expose themselves to this judgement more than necessary by telling their story repeatedly.

If they aren't already in the picture, research shows that *advocates are critical at this stage of the help-seeking process*. For young people, the concept of "talking to people who know my experience and understand my circumstances" is pivotal and very important to the participants when evaluating help⁵⁰. Advocates may be able to 'fast forward' the trust and relationship-building part of the engagement.

The kinds of information that may help children and young people understand whether the source of help is appropriate and accessible to them could include:

- The availability of advocates, and information on how they could get in touch with an advocate, or a way to leave information so an advocate can get in touch with them. Short bios/photos of advocates which highlights their shared experience would also be helpful.
- Short bios/photos of the people who they may be speaking with when they lay the complaint⁵¹.
- Examples of issues that others have complained about, particularly if these examples are given by other young people.
- Stories from other children and young people who have participated in a complaints process, detailing the journey and what happened at the end.

Children may not engage for fear they won't be believed or that there will be negative consequences or that the situation will require too much explanation.

Advocates are critical at this stage of the help-seeking process.

Information to assist young people to make a decision on engaging to make a complaint should include:

- The availability of advocates
- A description of who they will be speaking to when they lay the complaint
- Examples of issues others have complained about
- Stories of the journey of other children and young people.

⁵⁰ Johnson and Menna, 2017

⁵¹ Woodley et al., 2013

The role of helpers

Adolescents tend to seek help from trusted supports with whom they have established relationships. Generally, research has found that most young people prefer informal supports over formal supports⁵². Even when formal health and social service infrastructures exist, people seeking help generally prefer to rely on family and friends first and only subsequently turn to formal services.

For children and young people in care, caregivers are a key part of the help-seeking process.⁵³ Research has identified several common relationship factors that young people look for in helpers, such as knowing the source of support, closeness, liking them, having a long friendship, and mutual support. Young people have indicated that they are more likely to turn to someone for help if that person cares about them and is invested in meeting their needs⁵⁴.

Previous research with youth in care has found that they don't tend to distinguish between 'formal' and 'informal' helpers, instead, they look for support-specific characteristics of the person helping them, including how the helper interacts with and treats the young person (e.g. reliability, care, kindness, support, good listener, easy to talk to), how they treat the adolescent and their ability to keep things private. As stated above, shared experience and the ability of a helper to understand and empathise with what the young person is going through is also vital. Ultimately, however, trust, rather than the need for help is the key variable in determining whether a young person seeks help; a young person's perception of a potential helper as a good listener rather than simply proffering advice is central⁵⁵.

As illustrated in Figure 1, helpers are a key part of the helping journey. Those we talked to in phase one felt understanding and meeting the needs of helpers is important as they are likely

Young people prefer to rely on family and friends first.

Caregivers are a key part of the help-seeking process.

The personal characteristics of the helper are more important than their role; shared experience and empathy are critical qualities.

Meeting the needs of helpers, as well as children

⁵² Most of the literature defines 'formal' helpers as those who have a professional relationship with the child in care and are paid to care for them i.e. social workers, counsellors etc, however it's debateable whether this distinction is important for this project, so from here on we will refer to them simply as 'helpers.'

⁵³ Zima, B. T., Bussing, R., Yang, X., & Belin, T. R. (2000). Help seeking steps and service use for children in foster care. *The Journal of Behavioral Health Services & Research*, 27, 271-285. doi:10.1007/BF02291739

⁵⁴ Johnson, 2019

⁵⁵ Barker, 2007

to be not only a source of support and information for the children and young people but also may be the person who makes the complaint on their behalf. They told us that helpers can ensure a young person's safety, help them navigate and reassure them along the journey.

and young people, is important.

What are the enablers of help-seeking?

Generally, the literature is clear that the enablers of (and barriers to) help-seeking apply for any part of the journey. Enablers do, however, determine whether the child or young person has a positive or negative experience, which influences whether they advance through the stages of help-seeking or whether they fail to advance.

The literature talks about several personal factors that enable help-seeking for children and young people. Those who have confidence in their abilities to seek help, a willingness to accept help from others, knowing what help services available, previous good experiences with help-seeking and good social support are far more likely to seek help and stick with the process⁵⁶.

Personal factors (confidence, willingness to engage, good social support) are strongly associated with help-seeking.

In Aotearoa, research with more than 300 young people about seeking help to deal with crisis services found the young people wanted information in multiple formats and at multiple levels. Most had a low awareness of available services and needed help to be easily accessible when they needed it⁵⁷.

Information should be provided in multiple formats and at multiple levels.

Help-seeking may be facilitated by:

- Regularly reminding children and young people of their rights, and their right to do something if they are not happy. This should be provided at each contact with a social worker or advocate.⁵⁸
- Promoting the source of help as both helpful and trustworthy
- Enabling young people to get in touch anonymously, and promoting the privacy and confidentiality of the

⁵⁶ Johnson, 2019

⁵⁷ Woodley et al., 2011

⁵⁸ Oranga Tamariki Evidence Centre. (2018). Feedback and complaints systems: A rapid review. Wellington, New Zealand: Oranga Tamariki—Ministry for Children

service

- Being culturally responsive and respectful of religious or ethnic beliefs
- Making services easier to access
- Starting education about the availability of services at a young age,
- Using advertising to increase awareness of services
- Use of telephone helplines
- Promoting the relevant qualities and experiences of those who are there to help.

Research into internet-based help services found that young people used the internet for help because of the vast amounts of information available, it was easily accessed 24/7 (young males are far more likely to seek help after 11pm⁵⁹), information was easy to find, and it was fast, cheap and convenient.⁶⁰ A study of adolescents' use of online tools for mental health support found that they were significantly more likely to seek information online when in crisis.

People we interviewed felt that children and young people were more likely to seek help if they were told it's OK to use their voice. They would also want to know what will happen during the process, who they can talk with and who can support them.

Young people use the internet for help because the information is vast, easily accessed, fast, cheap and convenient.

What are the barriers to help seeking?

The research identifies several factors that might make young people reluctant to seek help or get in touch with help or engage in complaints processes:

- A lack of knowledge, awareness and information about available resources and services⁶¹
- Not knowing, or a lack of available information about the processes that take place when a young person gets in touch (males are less likely to get in touch when

⁵⁹ Burns JM, Davenport TA, Durkin LA, Luscombe GM, Hickie IB. The internet as a setting for mental health service utilisation by young people. *Med J Aust.* 2010 Jun 7;192(11 Suppl):S22–6

⁶⁰Horgan A, Sweeney J. Young students' use of the Internet for mental health information and support. *J Psychiatr Ment Health Nurs.* 2010 Mar;17(2):117–23. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2850.2009.01497.x

⁶¹ Kelliher, M. (2000). An exploration of the relationship between help-seeking behaviour and youth suicide prevention. Dunedin: University of Otago.

this information is not available⁶²⁾

- Uncertainty about confidentiality, often fuelled by a deep distrust of professionals⁶³
- Feelings of embarrassment, stigma, guilt and fear of opening up⁶⁴.
- Previous poor experience with help-seeking from professionals or services⁶⁵
- Not thinking there is a problem or being able to identify a problem⁶⁶
- Unfavourable content: information websites can be too technical to understand; some forums contain inaccurate information with people complaining and unhelpful; and finding the desired information on websites can be difficult⁶⁷
- Limited options for getting in touch: internet-only options are unsuitable if children and young people don't have access to data or appropriate technology, and a toll-free number may not work if children and young people don't realise, they can call free from public phones⁶⁸.

Barriers are also gendered: research with young people in Australia found that males are less likely to seek help from friends or the internet than females.

The people we interviewed felt there would be several barriers specific to children and young people in care that would prevent them from seeking help to express their dissatisfaction with aspects of their care. These barriers were:

- Lack of awareness of their rights, and a complaints process
- Inconsistent support people/helpers
- Reliving past trauma
- Lack of tools (e.g. phone, internet) to access a

Males are less likely to seek help than females.

⁶² ibid

⁶³ Woodley et al., 2013

⁶⁴ Fargas-Malet, M., & McSherry, D. (2017). The mental health and help-seeking behaviour of children and young people in care in Northern Ireland: Making services accessible and engaging. *British Journal of Social Work*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcx062>

⁶⁵ Ibid

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Kauer, S., Mangan, C., & Sancj, L. (2014). Do Online Mental Health Services Improve Help-Seeking for Young People? A Systematic Review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 16(3). doi:10.2196/jmir.3103

⁶⁸ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

complaints service

- Not wanting to 'dob in' people
- Concerns about their safety and confidentiality – often driven by a fear of reprisal
- A process which is too hard or overwhelming
- Fear of being judged, not believed or dismissed
- A lack of awareness about the Ombudsman and their role and not being able to distinguish between the Ombudsman and Oranga Tamariki.

The Complaints Process

Principles of effective complaints systems

Acknowledging and considering the views, opinions and concerns of children and young people is part of creating a complaints system which is focussed on the needs and best interests of the child or youth complainant⁶⁹.

Many of our interviewees felt that children and young people may not enter a complaints process for fear of not being believed. The Office of the Children's Commission is unequivocal that all complaints or grievances from children and young people need to be listened to and taken seriously:

Effectively, if a child feels that they have a complaint against a service then he or she has a sense of grievance, regardless of whatever others may think to the contrary. No proof is required. People, including children, generally know if they are dissatisfied with a service. (OCC, 2012 p. 16)

When a complaint is laid on behalf of a child or young person, the reviewer should seek the view of the child or young person provided they are physically and functionally able to communicate and/or an interview will not cause further trauma or psychological harm.

The active participation of children and young people in the

A child-friendly system provides opportunities for children and young people to express their views.

Children and young people need to be listened to and taken seriously.

Wherever possible, the view of the child or young person should be sought as part of the complaints process.

⁶⁹ Oranga Tamariki Evidence Centre, 2018

complaints process is important for their ongoing engagement. Research with children and young people in care found that they want their views to have a clear impact on decision-making.⁷⁰ To actively participate in the decision-making process, they need sufficient and appropriate information. Children and young people may feel disillusioned or frustrated if they feel their opinions have had no real impact on the decision-making process, leading to disengagement and disenfranchisement from the feedback or complaints system as a whole.

Our interviewees felt that meaningful engagement in a complaints process can be a powerful experience for children and young people in care. Knowing they are using their voice to advocate for themselves as well as help other young people can give them a sense of mastery and a feeling of being 'rights defenders' for others.

Effective complaints systems should promote restoration and reconciliation, as research on children and complaints suggests there is a disconnect between what adults perceive is a 'complaint' compared to what children and young people would like to complain or provide feedback about⁷¹.

Several interviewees felt that children and young people may wish to use mediation or restorative justice rather than proceeding with a formal complaint. This may be due to a need to not get someone 'in trouble', or an attempt to repair the situation and maintain a relationship with the person they are complaining about. Helping children understand that a complaint is a positive approach to problem-solving, rather than an adversarial process which requires punishment, may encourage more young people to make a complaint.

Language was also considered important by other interviewees who told us that the word 'complaint' could be replaced by terms such as "use your voice", "seeking support," or simply enabling children and young people in care to express their opinion or give feedback on things they think could make their life better. Researchers in England argue that a complaints

A child-friendly system includes the views of children and young people in decision-making.

Children and young people want to actively participate in decision-making and need good information to do this.

A child-friendly system promotes restoration and reconciliation.

Some children and young people may prefer a process more focussed on mediation and restoration, particularly if relationships may be damaged by the complaint.

Using words other than 'complaint' may encourage more young people to come forward.

⁷⁰ McLeod, A. (2006). Respect or empowerment? Alternative understandings of 'listening' in childcare social work. *Adoption and Fostering*, 30(4).

⁷¹ Ibid

system should be regarded as part of a positive feedback cycle with a focus on informing and improving service delivery, rather than a negative process which assigns blame⁷².

Tools used to receive complaints

There are some examples of different tools and methods used to collect complaints from children both in New Zealand and around the world. Generally, web pages and web-forms appear to be the main tool used to elicit complaints from children in care, with varying degrees of child- or even user-friendliness. Most sites are text heavy, with some complaint's forms requiring two or three click-throughs to get to the form (the link of which is often buried amongst text). Many sites don't appear to be mobile-friendly and very few speak directly to children and young people. There are very few tools aimed directly at eliciting feedback from children and young people in care, which are detailed below.

Currently, children and young people in care to leave can "feedback" via a web-based form on the Oranga Tamariki website.⁷³ Feedback can be "something is worrying you, or you feel Oranga Tamariki has not done something right. Or something good has happened that you'd like to share with us." Whilst the form has relatively few fields, it does ask children young people to give as much detail as possible, in writing. It's not clear on the general feedback form that there is a separate form for children and young people in care and it isn't easy to find on their website (a 3rd level page requiring two click throughs via "children in our care", then "information for children").

A search for "Oranga Tamariki complaints" brings up the general feedback, complaints, compliments and suggestions page. It's not clear who this page is for and there is no link to the aforementioned page for children. Complainants can fill out the online form, call a toll-free number (not a complaints hotline, simply the Oranga Tamariki main contact line) or pick

Web pages, web-based contact forms and email are the most used tools to elicit complaints and feedback from children and young people in care. The information on these pages is rarely, if ever, child-friendly or suitable for different communication needs.

The feedback form on the Oranga Tamariki website is difficult to find.

⁷² Butler, J. (2013). Getting the best from complaints: Social care complaints and representation for children, young people and others. London: Department for Education and Skills. [Link](#) to article.

⁷³ <https://www.orangatamariki.govt.nz/children-in-our-care/information-for-children/feedback-form/>

up a form from the nearest office.

Netsafe has an online form for people to report incidents, which is used in 78% of cases (incidents can also be reported by text (5%) phone (17%) or email (1%)). In general, Netsafe told us that incident reporting from children aged 11 and younger is mostly through parents; 11–13 is mostly through parents or a school on their behalf, 13–15 years are most likely to self-report an incident. Instagram was the main tool used to raise awareness of the incident reporting process.

In Western Australia, the UK and Canada, audio-computer-assisted self-interviewing (ACASI) is used to engage children and young people in care in planning for themselves and in providing feedback and complaints to assist service effectiveness and improvement. Self-interviewing has been identified as being of particular benefit to children and young people and is particularly useful for aiding literacy difficulties, with an enhanced sense of privacy and increased disclosure of sensitive information.⁷⁴ ACASI seems to improve quality of information by increasing response to sensitive questions, decreasing socially desirable responses, and by preventing null responses, and has been found a suitable method for data collection where formal education is low⁷⁵. The main tool used to collect feedback from children in care in Western Australia, the UK and Canada are provided by Viewpoint ACASI⁷⁶.

Mind of My Own is an app developed and used in the UK for children in care to express their views more clearly, get more involved in meetings and make better decisions with their social care team. Whilst not specifically a complaints tool, Mind of My Own is designed to deal with issues before they reach the complaints stage. Oranga Tamariki trialled Mind of My Own at four sites in 2018. A review of the trial found that:

- Whilst staff felt the app was generally easy to use and the training provided was good, there were some barriers to usage in terms of device and internet

Nearly 8 in 10 people who report incidents to Netsafe use the online form.

Young people aged 13 and over are more likely to self-report to Netsafe; younger children usually have support of an adult helper.

Giving feedback by self-interviewing (using a computer) is used in several jurisdictions for complaints from children in care. Evaluation has found this to be very effective.

Apps which allow ongoing feedback about care experiences are also used and have been trialled in NZ.

⁷⁴ Davies, M. & Morgan, A. (2005). Using Computer-Assisted Self-Interviewing (CASI) Questionnaires to Facilitate Consultation and Participation with Vulnerable Young People. *Child Abuse Review* 14, 389-406;

⁷⁵ Waruru, A & Nduati, R & Tylleskär, T. (2005). Audio computer-assisted self-interviewing (ACASI) may avert socially desirable responses about infant feeding in the context of HIV. *BMC medical informatics and decision making*. 5. 24. 10.1186/1472-6947-5-24.

⁷⁶ You can view a demonstration of ACASI [here](#)

- availability
- The web-based nature of the tool made it unsuitable for use in the secure, restricted access environment of the Youth Justice facilities
 - Most children who used the app used it on a single occasion, and there were limited examples of proactive use outside of social worker visits
 - Social workers saw the app as useful in engaging and getting to know children during a first meeting but not so useful with children with whom they already had a relationship
 - Whilst there are some examples of new information being gathered through Mind of My Own, this does not appear to have meaningfully impacted social worker practice or decision-making⁷⁷.

Making a complaint

Information

Child-friendly information on rights and complaints procedures should be simple and easy to read and include diagrams or pictures. Complaints guidelines compiled by the Commissioner for children and young people in Western Australia recommend that it is presented using formats such as websites, booklets, newsletters and social media (see page 51 for an analysis of child and teen social media use).

Care-experienced children and young people who participated in research by the Office of the Children's Commissioner wanted information in a format that they could keep and "have it everywhere". They asked for information that uses child-friendly language (smaller words, straightforward) and detailed simple steps. Bullet points, pictures and diagrams all help.

In terms of graphics, they wanted them to be "eye-catching", fun and interesting. Children and young people consulted by the Commissioner for Children and Young People in Western Australia suggested using oranges, blues and greens so that the process of complaining does not appear unfriendly or overly

Child-friendly complaints procedures should be easy to read and include diagrams and pictures.

Graphics should be eye-catching, fun and interesting. Colour should be used so the information appears friendly and informal.

⁷⁷ <https://orangatamariki.govt.nz/about-us/research/our-research/mind-of-my-own-review/>

formal, as well as using different language and graphics for younger children and adolescents.

Any information that is provided to children and young people prior to a complaint being made should outline:

- how to complain
- what information is required when they complain
- what assistance is available to them if they wish to make a complaint (e.g. advocacy)
- how the complaint will be managed (timeframes, progress reports, final advice)
- where the complainants can access the agency's complaints management policy and procedure⁷⁸.

This information needs to be provided to children in a way that can be understood by the very young and those with special needs (including physical, cognitive and behavioural challenges)⁷⁹.

For children with language or communication difficulties, or for whom English is not their preferred language, specialist help is likely to be required to ensure that they have equal access to the complaints system.

Interviewees advised that children and young people were more likely to make a complaint if the initial information requirements (from the child, young person or their helper) were minimal. They suggested initial information should consist of the following, with tick boxes used where appropriate:

- Name (or alias if they wish to make an anonymous complaint)
- Whether the contact is from a helper or a child or young person
 - If contact is from a child or young person, then advocacy services should be offered
- Preferred contact method
- Safe/appropriate times for contact
- Whether they would like an advocate to help with the process (suggested language from interviewees:

The amount of initial information required from the child or young person should be minimal, with tick boxes used where appropriate.

⁷⁸ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

⁷⁹ Ibid.

“Would you like someone who can support and walk alongside you and guide you through this process to get in touch?”)

Some thought should be given to accommodating help from peers or friends, particularly for teens who are more likely to refer to peers or friends for help. The presence of a friend may make the process less threatening for the complainant. In this instance, consideration should be given to communicating processes with the friend as they may be influential in helping the young person continue their engagement with the complaints process.

There may also be some value in allowing young people to externalise the complaint and lay a complaint on behalf of ‘a friend’. This depersonalises the experience and may make it less threatening. Interviewees suggested language such as “If you wish to contact us on behalf of yourself or someone else, please leave contact details here”.

Teens are more likely to enlist a friend for help; consideration should be given to communicating with both parties.

Enablers for complaining

Different communication formats

Multiple channels should be available for children, young people and their helpers to contact the Ombudsman:

- Social media messaging, including Instagram, Facebook messenger, Snapchat (although the temporary nature of these messages could be problematic), WhatsApp, Viber etc
- Text⁸⁰
- Email
- Phone hotlines
- Web-based contact form
- Web-based portal (although adding another layer with registration and passwords could be a barrier)
- On paper (letter)

Multiple communication channels should be available to submit complaints. Any channel should be free, reliable, and always generate a response that the complaint has been received.

⁸⁰ Social media messaging is often preferable to text as young people don't need credit to respond – they just need to find a free Wi-Fi connection.

- Through an advocate.

Child-friendly⁸¹ formats for making complaints include social media messaging, email, text, phone, in person or the ability to submit multimedia (i.e. film or social media 'story').

Interviewees suggested that the Ombudsman consider ways that young people can compose a case or story and add to it over time, sharing it when they are ready. This is a concept familiar to young people who use Facebook or Instagram to build stories over time.

Any complaints channels, including hotlines, need to be free, reliable, and always generate a response⁸².

Advocate support

The role of an advocate in a complaints process is to provide children and young people with the information they need and support them to understand and interpret that information⁸³. The advocate can focus on the child or young person's views and wishes and act in their best interests⁸⁴. A 2018 review of effective complaints systems by Oranga Tamariki found that an advocacy service is an important support of accessible feedback and complaints processes⁸⁵.

The personal characteristics of an advocate are the same as for other helpers; however, an advocate also needs to be aware relevant legislation, complaints policies and procedures, and privacy and confidentiality obligations.

Our interviewees described advocates as helpers with a shared experience of care, and a knowledge of the complaints system and how to navigate it, and someone who can help the child or young person formulate or broker a complaint. Some felt that advocates were key regardless of whether the child or young person had another helper alongside them. The Office of the Children's Commission, however, warns against making an

Advocates are important even if the young person has a helper alongside.

Advocates should be recommended but not required to proceed with a complaint.

⁸¹ Generally, any information here applies to children, young people and their helpers/supporters

⁸² Oranga Tamariki Evidence Centre, 2018

⁸³ Office of the Children's Commissioner, 2012

⁸⁴ Elsley, S. (2010). 'Advocacy makes you feel brave': Advocacy support for children and young people in Scotland. Scottish Government. <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2010/01/07144331/0>

⁸⁵ Oranga Tamariki Evidence Centre. (2018).

advocate a requirement for making a complaint as this may exacerbate the existing power imbalance between children and adults; although many participants in their research felt that they wouldn't be taken seriously unless they were supported by an adult⁸⁶.

If not already engaged, then advocate support should be offered when the young person makes a complaint.

In addition to advocate support, several interviewees believed that more formal support should be offered to children and young people going through a complaints process, such as access to counselling or therapy.

Traversing the process

The literature is very clear on the principles behind an effective complaints process for children and young people⁸⁷. It must:

- 1) have clear and reasonable time limits
- 2) be transparent and easily understood
- 3) have strict confidentiality policies and practices
- 4) have good staff training
- 5) be culturally safe.

These principles are expanded on below.

1. An effective complaints process has clear and reasonable time limits

According to The International Organization for Standardization (ISO, 2004, as cited in OCC, 2012) complaints need to meet clear and reasonable time limits, which are communicated to, and able to be understood by, children and young people, and take into account children's perspectives on time. Interestingly, research shows that compared to adults' children perceive the passage of time as slower, meaning that

Children perceive the passage of time as slower, therefore complaints timelines for children may need to be shorter

⁸⁶ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

⁸⁷ See, for example Oranga Tamariki Evidence Centre (2018), Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

complaints systems timelines need to be shorter for children and young people than for adults. The review by Oranga Tamariki suggests:

Based on a comparison of international good practice, a suggested timeframe for complaints resolution should be straightaway where possible, and within one week generally. Formal resolution should take no longer than five weeks, although further independent review may take longer depending on the complexity of the complaint, anywhere up to ten weeks, with appeals to an ombudsman even longer⁸⁸.

Some of those we spoke to in phase one felt the timing of the process would need careful management by the Ombudsman, particularly if the office is reliant on Oranga Tamariki to process the complaint. Others said that helping children and young people understand the timing and what will happen next is very important for keeping them engaged with the process.

Children and young people need to know what happens next

2. Is transparent and easily understood

Any complaint system for children and young people needs to be as simple and straightforward as possible. There is general agreement that good practice in working with children and young people's complaints is in finding speedy, constructive, and agreeable solutions to the complaint as close to the point of service delivery as possible⁸⁹. Formal procedures should also, however, be in place if the complaint cannot be resolved at the local level, and these procedures should be communicated as simply as possible.

Complaints systems for children need to be as simple and straightforward as possible.

Complainants need to be kept updated throughout the process as to what is happening and when. There should be little, if any, hand-off between agencies to keep the process clear. When action is taken or decisions are made need to be clearly documented and communicated.

Complainants need to be kept updated throughout the process.

Interviewees suggested that helping children understand the process before the complaints process is underway – possibly

Graphics may help complainants understand the journey

⁸⁸ Oranga Tamariki, 2018, p. 14

⁸⁹ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

through a graphic journey map – could be valuable.

3. Strict confidentiality policies and practices

A perceived lack of confidentiality is one of the greatest barriers to raising complaints or concerns. Confidentiality procedures should be clear to both the children and young people, and staff who are handling the complaint.

Children and young people will not complain if they think their confidentiality will be breached.

4. Good staff training

Staff should be trained in:

- How to handle complaints with sensitivity, respect, and courtesy.
- Cultural safety, and how to make a complaints process accessible and welcoming to children and young people from all cultural backgrounds.
- Confidentiality principles.
- Interviewing or communicating with children and young people who have experienced harm or trauma
- Interviewing or communicating with young people who have communication difficulties (e.g. talking mats).
- Interviewing or communicating with vulnerable children and young people, such as those who are living with disabilities, homeless, members of minority groups, refugees or new migrants⁹⁰.
- How to maintain transparency with the young person and manage their expectations in terms of what is and isn't possible
- How, when and in what ways to involve whānau when appropriate.

All staff who interface with children and young people as part of the complaints process should be trained.

5. Cultural safety

Cultural backgrounds inform and influence the way young people experience services, how they perceive, experience and

Cultural safety is a vital component of a complaints process.

⁹⁰ See page 34 of this report "Communicating with Children and Young People" for more information

resolve issues⁹¹, and how they interact with adults.

Those we spoke to have much experience of working with care-experienced tamariki and rangatahi Māori, as well as children from Pacific and refugee and migrant backgrounds. They told us that *cultural safety is vital to identity*, and it is critical that this is not eroded. An ecological and holistic approach, using and incorporating whakawhānaungatanga (nurturing relationships), manaakitanga (care) and kaitiakitanga (guardianship, trust) in interactions with young people particularly for tamariki and rangatahi Māori, will aid in understanding the context of children and young people's lives across different settings, not just in the service they are expressing their dissatisfaction about.

Our interviewees told us that some Māori and Pacific children are more likely to complain through their behaviour than through written or spoken language. They will "break a window" or "run-away" to express their dissatisfaction with a person or situation; in these instances, it's likely that they've tried previously to express themselves through language which has not been successful. Behaviour, therefore, should not be used to exclude children and young people from a complaints process, as the behaviour may stem from the reasons behind the complaint.

We heard from our interviewees that Pacific young people are unlikely to participate in a complaints process if the focus is on the word "complain", however they may participate in a "justice" or "rebalancing" process.

Complaining is not a Pacific value, in our world view you kind of just suck it up and stick with whatever you've got (interviewee).

This is also an experience shared by the Human Rights Commission⁹² that found that although Pacific peoples were likely to experience discrimination, they were unlikely to lay a complaint. This was due to cultural customs and traditions such as respect for authority, obedience, and deference or *va fealofa'i* – knowing one's place.

Some Māori and Pacific children and young people express their dissatisfaction physically rather than verbally.

Pacific children and young people are unlikely to complain if the word 'complain' is used

⁹¹ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

⁹² Walker, P (n.d) Pacific People Don't Complain But It's Not Because There's No Problem: New Zealand. Human Rights Commission

We heard that refugee and migrant families are likely to complain to each other if they are unhappy yet will rarely if ever come forward with a formal complaint. Helping them understand that the complaints process is safe and confidential is a priority as they are highly unlikely to enter a complaints process for fear of state reprisal (i.e. deportation).

Refugee and migrant families may not complain due to fear of state reprisal.

Engaging with children and young people in person

Our interviewees who are experienced in interviewing vulnerable children and young people had some advice for in-person contact with young people, particularly when it comes to eliciting information or recording complaints.

Child-centred principles discussed elsewhere in this document, such as taking time to build trust, displaying empathy, listening, ensuring a trusted person/advocate is present, active listening without judgement and ensuring confidentiality apply to all interviews or in-person contact with children and young people.

Prior to the interview, those we spoke with recommended that the interviewer does some background work – ideally with an advocate or trusted person who is supporting the complainant. At this stage it would be valuable to check any known previous traumas to help determine a safe person to do the interview, and to check with the child or young person who they want to be present (i.e. one or all of sibling/s, advocate, caregiver, parent, other helper).

Ideally, an adult familiar with the child or young person could conduct the interview, however this may require some workforce training. If this wasn't possible, then some communication assistance (i.e. from people trained in communication needs of care experienced children and young people) could be brought in.

Communicating with the support people about their role (i.e. who can speak for the child or young person?) may also be helpful at this stage. The interviewer should also work with the advocate or trusted person to understand any behavioural or emotional triggers.

When speaking with a child or young person *kanohi ki te kanohi*:

- Use a trusted person or advocate
- Check previous trauma to avoid triggers
- Use communication assistance where required
- For Māori and Pacific children beginning with a prayer or *karakia* may be appropriate
- Do not face the child or young person directly
- Do not expect eye contact
- Use props to help tell the story (e.g. post-it notes, talking mats)
- Do not expect immediate, full disclosure of sensitive issues.

For Māori and Pacific children and young people, starting the interview with a karakia or prayer, particularly one focussed on the intention of the meeting (e.g. safety, confidentiality, voice restoration) may be appropriate. After this, a brief explanation of confidentiality, safety and orienting them to the process is useful.

The word 'interview', where people sit around a table or facing each other or in a circle of chairs, may not accurately reflect what the interview might look like. Those we spoke with recommend that, if possible, meetings should take place in a safe space of the young person's choosing. The interviewer should sit next to or near, not opposite, the child or young person to minimise eye contact (in an online interview this may be achieved by turning off the camera). They also recommended (as has been covered in the methods section) that the interviewer and young person participate in an activity together (e.g. drawing or building for younger children).

Using props to help establish the story, such as talking mats (especially helpful for younger children or older children/young people with FASD⁹³, ASD⁹⁴ or other intellectual or communication difficulties), or post-it notes to track the story for adolescents are also useful tools and provide a physical distraction from the intensity of an interview process.⁹⁵

Our interviewees felt that the adult who was communicating with the young person should be aware that children and young people who have experienced trauma may not communicate if the adult reminds them of someone who has caused them harm. They also warned that full disclosure of sensitive issues can take time particularly if in the past adults have been unreliable.

After the complaints process has ended or the complaint is resolved

Interviewees suggested that the complaints process is ended with a feedback loop, giving young people opportunities to

⁹³ Fetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorder

⁹⁴ Autism Spectrum Disorder

⁹⁵ Talking Trouble in Auckland offers training in using Talking Mats

input into the process and their experience.

The table below, sourced from the review by Oranga Tamariki in 2018, suggests what data should be collected, and the purpose of the data⁹⁶.

Figure 3: Complaints data (source: Oranga Tamariki)

Data	Purpose
Demographic information about children and young people giving feedback or making complaints, such as age or ethnicity.	Inform the agency as to the accessibility of the process e.g. if there are no or few complaints from children or young people involved with youth justice, then this may suggest an accessibility issue.
The form of complaints, such as the total number of complaints, method used to lay complaint, geographical region the complaint originated, service arm which the complaint relates to.	Inform the agency as to the accessibility of the process, whether the available methods are used or useful
The content of complaints.	Tracking, monitoring and analysing complaint data can reveal systemic and recurring issues and trends.
Timeframes and process information such as decisions made, the rationale behind these decisions, and when actions were taken.	Allows the agency to track adherence to the timeliness standards (e.g. the number of days before a complaint is formally acknowledged) and the quality of decision-making.
The outcome of complaints, e.g. actions on the part of the agency, whether the complainant was satisfied, whether the complaint was escalated, whether a change was made to the complaints process or service delivery).	Allows the agency to assess the quantity and quality of complaint resolutions, and document actions taken to improve complaint policy and processes as well as overall service quality.

A process for babies, and children and young people who cannot speak for themselves

One of the more perplexing issues we encountered, both in our interviews and the literature, is the participation in complaints processes of those who cannot communicate their interests and rights, such as babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves due to disability. A recurring theme in the literature is the perceptions of the capacity, or incapacity, of these children to decide for themselves⁹⁷. Their general positioning in society as vulnerable, needy and dependent is sometimes used as an excuse to not consult with

⁹⁶ There is more information relating to complaints data protocols and procedures that we can include – however this is likely something that doesn't need further explanation in this context.

⁹⁷ Office Of The Children's Commissioner, 2012

them and therefore denies them the right to voice an opinion⁹⁸. In that instance, it can be asked “What would the child want if he/she could decide for him or herself?”. Critics of this position, however, argue that adults cannot know what these children will decide unless they are able to make themselves aware of children’s views⁹⁹.

The biggest issue for babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves is understanding who has the right to speak on their behalf. Ordinarily, as those who cannot speak for themselves may not be competent to exercise their rights, the caretaker then assumes responsibility for protecting these rights. In this case, the onus is on the caretaker to “choose what the child would choose if competent to make choices and choose with regard to the interests of the adult the child will become”¹⁰⁰. The issue is complicated, however, where the caretaker is Oranga Tamariki and the child is part of a wider whānau who also believe they have a voice in what the child would choose if they were competent to make their own choices. It becomes even more complicated when we consider the recent findings of the Office of the Children’s Commissioner in the report *Te Kuku O Te Manawa – Ka puta te riri, ka momori te ngākau, ka heke ngā roimata mo tōku pēpi*, which found some decisions made by Oranga Tamariki were not in the best interests of the child, or the adult they would become, such as the mother who was pressured into having an abortion (p.53), or the harm caused to the physical and emotional wellbeing of pēpi due to their involvement in the care and protection system¹⁰¹.

Our interviewees had very few answers as to how this may be resolved but did have several ideas relating to principles and processes that could be taken into account when considering complaints from (or on behalf of) the unborn, babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves. These were:

- There may need to be a separate process for receiving

It needs to be clear who can speak on behalf of babies and very young children in care if they can’t speak for themselves.

The Office of the Children’s Commissioner found that Oranga Tamariki did not always act in the best interests of the child or the adult they would become.

⁹⁸ Te One, S. (2011) Defining rights: Children’s rights in theory and in practice. *He Kupu | The Word* 2(4) 41-57 [Link](#)

⁹⁹ Taylor, N. J., Smith, A. B., & Nairn, K. (2001). Rights important to young people: Secondary students and staff perspectives. *International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 9, 137-156

¹⁰⁰ Archard 1993, p.14, cited in Te One, 2011

¹⁰¹ Refer back to the discussion on childhood toxic stress and its later impact on adult health and development on page 7.

complaints from babies, young children and minors who cannot speak for themselves.

- Part of the process should be understanding the motivations of the adult making the complaint and what they or the child stand to benefit. Is it in the best interests of the child?
- The process should collect the voices of others around the child (biological parents, whānau, caregivers).
- The potential for lifelong harm to infants, particularly those up to two months old, means the process and resolution must be fast¹⁰².
- As with children and young people, an advocate is critical, particularly to represent the interests of the child.

¹⁰² For more, see <https://www.childtrauma.org/>

General principles

Principles of communicating with children and young people

UNICEF has identified four central principles for producing information and communications for children. They are:

- 1. Communication for children should be age-appropriate and child-friendly. It should:**
 - Use child-appropriate language, characters, stories, music and humour.
 - Encourage and model positive interaction and critical thinking; and
 - Use special effects judiciously and wisely.
- 2. Communication for children should address the child holistically. It should**
 - Use an integrated rather than single-issue approach to communication.
 - Offer positive models for adults in their relationships with children as full human beings in their own right; and
 - Create "safe havens" i.e. emphasise the good in people, modelling warmth and care.
- 3. Communication for children should be positive and strengths-based. It should:**
 - Build self-confidence as well as competence
 - Use positive modelling
 - Include children as active citizens learning about and modelling social justice
 - Do no harm.
- 4. Communication for children should address the needs of all, including those who are most disadvantaged. It should:**
 - Reflect the dignity of every child and adult.

General principles of communication with children and young people:

1. It should be age-appropriate and child-friendly
2. Should address the child holistically
3. Should be positive and strengths-based
4. Should address the needs of all, including those who are most disadvantaged.

- Be inclusive: celebrate and value all types of diversity
- Ensure communication is free of stereotypes
- reflect and nurture the positive aspects of local cultures and traditions.

Communication and developmental ages and stages

Early years (birth through 6 years)

Whilst communication around complaints for the younger years group is likely to be targeted at carers (e.g. caregivers, whānau, health practitioners, early childhood educators), it is possible to start educating children in their early years on their rights through developmentally appropriate books, songs and other simple media.

Communications for this age should be designed for dual audiences (e.g. both adults and children). Adult-child interaction should be encouraged, for example books that could be read to children by adults.

There are multiple developmental and health concerns for young children regarding digital media (e.g. obesity, self-regulation) and technology and technological solutions aimed at this age group should be used sparingly¹⁰³.

Middle years (7 to 10 years)

For many children, the middle years are when they acquire more sophisticated language and literacy skills and they are likely to be influenced by what they see and hear at home, at school and in their community. Children this age, particularly once they reach 9 or 10 years, are better able to distinguish between fantasy and reality and develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills.

At this age, they are likely to understand and pay attention to child-centred stories and characters and may participate in interactive problem solving. Many may have reasonable technical abilities and can navigate technology such as the

Children in early years can be educated on their rights through books and songs.

Technology aimed at 0-6 years should be used sparingly

Middle years children should respond well to positive child role models which show children making a difference to themselves and others.

¹⁰³ Council on Communications And Media (2016) Media and Young Minds *Paediatrics* Nov 2016, 138 (5) e20162591; DOI: 10.1542/peds.2016-2591

internet or smartphone apps. They may also be receptive to stories which offer strong positive child role models which show children making a difference in their own and other children's lives¹⁰⁴.

Early adolescence (11 to 14 years)

Older children/younger teens are likely to look to siblings, friends and peers (rather than adults) for support. At this stage they begin to gather information independently, so information needs to meet their (and their peers') developmental needs rather than adult helpers.

Some children this age may have undiagnosed communication needs, and they may also not want these to be 'exposed'. In this instance, high interest, low literacy alternatives (graphics, sound) should be offered to compensate for any reading or comprehension difficulties. As with younger children, social justice or social heroes (people who make a difference) will appeal as will humour and creativity. There is a caveat, however, children this age can be quick to detect that they are being patronised and will not appreciate being 'talked down to'¹⁰⁵.

Later adolescent and onwards (15 years +)

Recent New Zealand research with adolescents with experience with youth justice found that:

- Communication is often transactional; young people will participate if there is a purpose and something to be gained
- Young people may be unaware of their speech, language and communication needs
- Institutional language and jargon should not be used. Language should be tested on young people before release¹⁰⁶.

Both younger and older teens should respond to communication that is high interest, low literacy (e.g. graphics, sound) providing it is not patronising or doesn't appear to be 'dumbed down.'

¹⁰⁴ Kolucki, B and Lemish, D (2011) Communicating with Children: Practices to Nurture, Inspire, Excite, Educate and Heal: UNICEF

¹⁰⁵ Bradbury-Jones, C. et al, 2018.

¹⁰⁶ Metzger et al., 2017

Technology

Access to technology and the internet

Around eight in 10 New Zealand children in 2018 reported they could access the internet when they want or need to. Internet access increases progressively with age; around half of all 9-year olds (53%) report they can access the internet, compared to 93% of 17-year olds¹⁰⁷.

Research by Netsafe in 2018 found that:

- The most common places for children to access the internet are at home (96%) and at school (89%)
- Children and young people use multiple, preferably portable, digital devices to go online
- Overall, the most used devices are laptop or notebook computers (76%), and smartphones (72%); among older children (15-17 years) smartphones are the most frequently used device (93%)
- Younger children (9-11 years) are less confident in managing privacy than other age groups; children and teens aged 11 and over are confident about their digital skills
- Most children use the internet for entertainment, learning, and socialising; 9Nine out of 10 watch video clips at least once a week.
- Children are much less likely to go online for community engagement, civic participation and creative opportunities.

Research shows that digital disadvantage affects already vulnerable groups. People living in social housing, people with disabilities, Pasifika and Māori have a higher likelihood of digital exclusion.

2019 research by the Vodafone Foundation and InternetNZ found that internet accessibility was essential to most young people's daily routines, –even those who faced significant

93% of 17-year-olds report that they can access the internet.

Children and young people are most likely to access the internet at school and home, using portable digital devices (especially smartphones).

Digital disadvantage disproportionately affects people in social housing, those with disabilities, Māori and Pasifika.

¹⁰⁷ Pacheco, E and Melhuish, N. (2019), Exploring New Zealand Children's Technology Access, Use, Skills and Opportunities. Evidence From Ngā Taiohi Matihiko O Aotearoa - New Zealand Kids Online [Link](#)

barriers around accessibility and access to online technologies. Not having internet access can therefore have a disproportionately harmful impact on these groups (such as children in care) who are experiencing social exclusion in other ways.

Those in social housing and people with disabilities appear to be particularly disadvantaged with respect to internet access. In 2017, just 69% of those living in Housing NZ or other social housing report having access to the internet, compared with 91% reporting access across all respondents (in the 2017 NZ Electoral Survey). Similarly, the same report found that only 71% of people with disabilities report having access to the internet. In the 2018 NZ Crime and Victims Survey, 17% of people with disabilities report having no internet access compared to the full sample where just 5% had no internet access. The same report also found that Māori (12.23%) and Pasifika (10.55%) reported they did not have internet access in 2017¹⁰⁸.

A survey carried out in September 2019 by Network for Learning found that one-quarter of students in deciles 1-3 schools had no home internet access¹⁰⁹. It showed that students least likely to access the internet at home were those living in low-income households, Māori and Pacific students, and those living in rural areas. This situation changed after the Covid-19 lockdown, however, with more than 25,000 students getting access to devices and the internet, with children in low decile schools given priority access¹¹⁰.

The experience of those we spoke to suggests that there is equity issues related to access to both technology and the internet for children and young people in care. Some seemed to think that children in care had poor access to technology, particularly phones. We heard from one organisation that young people in care had been given phones during the first Covid-19 lockdown, of which 90% had been stolen, broken, sold or given away by the end of the lockdown period. When they do have phones, young people in care may lack money to pay

Students in deciles 1-3 schools are less likely to have internet access; however, this may have changed over Covid-19 with children at low decile schools getting priority access to the internet and devices.

Children in care may have poor access to technology – however no hard data exists to prove or disprove this.

¹⁰⁸ Digital inclusion and wellbeing in New Zealand (nd) New Zealand Govt [Link](#)

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.n4i.co.nz/new-survey-provides-insight-into-schools-technology-challenges-and-plans/>

¹¹⁰ <https://thespinoff.co.nz/society/vodafone/07-08-2020/disconnected-under-lockdown-what-digital-inequality-looks-like-in-a-pandemic/>

for Wi-Fi or data. We heard that rural broadband coverage is often problematic for children and young people in care, with patchy coverage and difficulty connecting.

Several of those we spoke to would often let young people in care use their phones to access the internet. When they did so, connecting with their friends on social media was a top priority. As one person told us: "*When kids in care get access to tech, they don't want to complain, they want to connect with their mates.*"

We were told that for children and young people to use technology to initiate a complaints process they would need unfiltered access to devices so they can complain/disclose 'alone' and where the use of the device for this purpose can't be tracked.

We also heard that most children and young people in care (other than those in youth justice residences) should have access to technology at school through laptops, Chromebooks and tablets. Videoconferencing through applications such as Zoom is increasingly used and works well for older teens.

Unfiltered access to devices is needed so children and young people can report or disclose in privacy if they wish.

Social media use

Children and young people

Overseas research conducted in 2019 suggests that more than half of teens (54%) get their news and information from social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook and Twitter, and half (50%) get their news from YouTube¹¹¹.

Research by Netsafe in 2018 found that social media is ubiquitous among children of all ages who use these tools primarily for socialising and entertainment. Children and young people use multiple social media platforms; 4 in 10 NZ teens aged between 14 and 17 use five or more social media tools. One quarter (25%) use YouTube, Facebook and Snapchat (23% each), and Messenger and Instagram (13% and 11%,

YouTube, TikTok, Snapchat, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter are primary sources of news and information for young people.

¹¹¹ Common Sense Media (Aug 2019) New Survey Reveals Teens Get Their News from Social Media and YouTube. Press Release [Link](#)

respectively). Interestingly, males were twice as likely to use YouTube than females (33% compared with 16%). Females were twice as likely to use Instagram and Snapchat than males. The research also found that older teens (16–17 years) were more likely to use Facebook and Messenger than younger teens.¹¹² Note that, as above, TikTok and Snapchat have grown market share considerably in the last two years¹¹³.

TikTok and Snapchat are becoming increasingly influential in the dissemination of news and information – whilst there are no comparable NZ statistics, Snapchat currently reaches 90% of 13–24 year olds in the US¹¹⁴. TikTok is another interesting emerging platform, with the Washington Post starting to get some traction among teens for its [TikTok creations](#), which employ humour and creativity and a reasonable amount of social awareness and commentary on racism, politics and social justice.

In New Zealand (January 2020), 13–17-year olds made up 4.3% of the overall social media advertising market¹¹⁵.

Online safety

Not all teens are confident around online safety. In the Netsafe survey, one in five teens with disabilities (21%) said they knew “not that much” about keeping safe and secure online, compared to teens without impairments (11%). Similarly, Pacific (26%) and Māori teens (17%) reported knowing “not that much” about online safety, in contrast with other ethnic groups such as European/Pākehā (9%).

General population use of social media

Social media in New Zealand is dominated by YouTube and Facebook. In Jan 2020, 88% of all internet users aged 16-64 used YouTube, with 84% using Facebook although Facebook use is declining among NZ youth, possibly due to the increased

TikTok and Snapchat are steadily increasing in market share and influence, particularly with young people.

Kids content – primarily Cartoon Network Australia – makes up three of YouTubes

¹¹² Pacheco, E., and Melhuish N (2018) New Zealand teens' digital profile: A factsheet New Zealand teens' digital profile: A factsheet. Netsafe Link

¹¹³ Whilst there are no specific data related to NZ for TikTok, worldwide use has grown by 87.5% since January 2017

¹¹⁴ <https://www.poynter.org/business-work/2019/cohort15/>

¹¹⁵ <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2020-new-zealand>

use of TikTok and Snapchat. In Jan 2018, kids' content made up three of YouTube's most popular media-run channels (across all audience segments), the largest of which was [Cartoon Network Australia](#), which suggests that the style of presentation appeals to most audience segments.

most popular media-run channels for all audiences.

Information from the data report 2020 shows that in New Zealand in January 2020¹¹⁶:

- Facebook Messenger was the most active messenger app
- Internet penetration is estimated to be 93%, with 3.6 million or 75% of the population actively using social media
- The use of mobile phones to access the internet increased by 28% in 2019, whilst laptops and desktops dropped by 15%
- 94% of internet users aged 16–64 use the internet to watch online videos

Nearly every user of the internet in New Zealand watches online videos

Figure 4: Screenshot of Cartoon Network Australia

¹¹⁶ <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2020-new-zealand>

Appendices

Appendix One: UN Declarations

The International Human Rights Framework for Indigenous Children and Youth

The UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) protects the rights of indigenous children and youth. Article 21 and 22 of the Declaration call for particular attention to indigenous children and youth, when implementing the UN Declaration – and when taking measures to improve the economic and social conditions of indigenous peoples. Further, the Declaration gives the right to live in freedom, peace and security, including protecting children from being removed from their group by force (Article 7.2), the right to all levels of education without discrimination (Article 14.2), the right to be protected from economic exploitation or hazardous work and the right to be protected for violence and discrimination (Article 22.2).

The Convention of the Rights of the Child (CRC) covers indigenous children and youth and include specific references to indigenous children in ensuring their access to diverse media in their languages (Article 17.d), to education that is non-discriminatory (Article 29.d) and the right to own culture, religion and language (Article 30).

Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)

Article 7 – Children with disabilities

1. States Parties shall take all necessary measures to ensure the full enjoyment by children with disabilities of all human rights and fundamental freedoms on an equal basis with other children.
2. In all actions concerning children with disabilities, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration.
3. States Parties shall ensure that children with disabilities have the right to express their views freely on all matters affecting them, their views being given due weight in accordance with their age and maturity, on an equal basis with other children, and to be provided with disability and age-appropriate assistance to realize that right.

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